

Analysis of retro-nasal flavour of beef pate using a chewing simulator

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Abstract

In the case of retro-nasal aroma, since the aroma compounds released from the food during chewing are targeted, the change of the food structure during chewing (crushing, grinding, disintegration, melting, dilution by saliva, etc.) strongly influences the release and thus the perception. In this study, the relation between retro-nasal flavour and food deliciousness based on the physicochemical properties of flavour was examined. Beef pate was used as a model to study flavour release under controlled in vitro mastication and salivation conditions considering the consumption of solid foods and elderly people, using a chewing simulator. In addition, with the recent aging society, the number of elderly people who cannot enjoy eating due to the deterioration of eating function has been increasing. The decrease in masticatory ability, muscle weakness of the swallowing muscles, and changes in saliva composition and secretion volume contributed to a decrease in taste, smell, and other perceptions. Also, in this study, the effect of these oral parameters on flavour release under controlled chewing and saliva conditions considering the eating of the elderly person was further examined by the utilization of the chewing simulator. Through these studies, it was found that the effect of coexisting ingredients such as beef fat on the time course behaviour of aroma release, it was confirmed that the release curve of middle and last type aromas in particular changed depending on the strength of chewing and fat content. Considering the model saliva of the elderly, it is presumed that the lowering of the flavour sensation in the elderly is also caused by the change of the saliva composition.

Keywords: aroma release, pate, chewing simulator, fat content, elderly

Introduction

Olfactory sensation is the sensation produced by the interactions of aroma compounds with receptors of the olfactory cells on the olfactory epithelium at the top of the nasal cavity. It is also possible to feel the flavour when eating and drinking food by putting it in your mouth. This is called a retro-nasal aroma, aroma compounds radiated from the food in the oral cavity reaching the nasal cavity through the respiratory tract to be sensed. In the case of retro-nasal aroma, since the aroma compounds released from the food during chewing are targeted, the change of the food structure during chewing (crushing, grinding, disintegration, melting, dilution by saliva, etc.) strongly influences the release and thus the perception. In this study, the relation between retro-nasal flavour and food deliciousness based on the physicochemical properties of flavour was examined. Beef pate was used as a model to study the flavour release under controlled in vitro mastication and salivation conditions considering the consumption of solid foods and elderly people, using a chewing simulator [1] to analyse multiple samples without individual differences in the contribution of flavour during mastication of solid materials. In this presentation, the effect of these oral parameters on flavour release under controlled chewing and saliva conditions considering the eating of the elderly person was further examined by the utilization of the chewing simulator.

Experimental

Materials

Beef pate was prepared as follow. Minced beef lean meat 50g was placed in a mould and shaped. Then, it was grilled with a 180-degree Celsius hot plate for 3 minutes in the front and 2 minutes in the back. Crushed pate with added aroma compounds was placed in a mould and shaped. High-fat samples in which 10% and 20% of bovine fat were added, were also prepared and examined.

Each aroma compound was added such as the final concentration was 0.1% (1000ppm) as shown in Table 1.

The standard artificial saliva [2, 3] was dissolved by blending NaHCO₃: 5.20g, K₂HPO₄: 1.36g, NaCl: 0.88g, KCl: 0.48g, CaCl₂: 0.44g, Mucin (M1778-10g, from porcine stomach) 2.16g into 1L of milli-Q water.

PTR-TOF-MS

The drift tube of a PTR-TOF 8000 (Ionicon, Innsbruck, Austria) was kept under controlled conditions of pressure (2.3 mbar), temperature (50° Celsius) and voltage (480 V) resulting in a field density ratio (E/N) of 110

Td (E being the electric field strength and N the gas number density; $1 \text{ Td} = 10^{-17} \text{ V cm}^2$). Detected aroma compounds and ions were as shown in Table.1

Table 1: PTR-MS detected compounds and ions.

Compounds name	m/z	Log ow	Log aw
methanethiol (MeSH)	49.011	0.78	-0.89
butanoic acid	89.0597	0.79	4.66
furfural	98.0318	0.41	3.81
dimethyl trisulfide (DMTS)	128.966	1.87	1.12
nonanal	143.143	4.79	1.52

Log ow: oil-water partition coefficient; Log aw: air-water partition coefficient

Chewing Simulator

The samples used were 5g pate pieces. The operating condition of the chewing simulator was basically Force: 25daN and Share Angle: 2 degrees unless otherwise stated. The influx of artificial saliva into chewing simulator was carried out at a setting of 1ml/min. The data were run in n=5 and averaged. Nitrogen flow to chewing simulator was carried out at 70 ml/min. Varying chewing simulator operation conditions was as follows. Force: 25daN, Share Angle: 2 degrees (weak chewing), and Force: 30daN, Share Angle: 3 degrees (normal chewing)

Data Processing

PTR-MS flavour release curves were processed in the following manner. Slope of the Nth chewing: Relative peak intensity of the Nth mastication/peak intensity of the first mastication, I_{max}: Maximum peak intensity, T_{max}: Number of mastication showing maximal peak intensity

Results and discussion

Using PTR-MS, we examined the aroma release behaviour of the samples for which the chewing strength and fat content in the pate were changed. From T_{max} results shown in Figure 1a, the flavour release became faster when the strength of chewing was increased (T_{max} decrease) and became slower when the lipid content was increased (T_{max} increase) The flavour release tended to be faster for 20% of lipids. I_{max} results showed that the release amount increased when the strength of mastication increased, and the release amount decreased when the lipid content increased. Figure.1b showed that the flavour release became faster when the strength of mastication increased, and the flavour release became slower when the lipid content increased.

Figure 1a: Changes in aroma release due to differences in the strength of mastication and the amount of fat.

Figure 1b: Changes in aroma release due to differences in the strength of mastication and the amount of fat.

Confirmation based on the saliva composition and saliva flow rate of the elderly people as shown in Table 2 were used to model elderly flavour release. As a result of Figure 2, in salivary compositions 2 and 3, the flavour release of all compounds was delayed due to the increase in Tmax, and the decrease in I_{max} was also observed, thereby confirming the tendency of the intensity to be suppressed. In addition, it was confirmed that a change in the saliva flow rate influences a change in the flavour release more than a change in the mucin amount. It is presumed that these are largely due to the decrease in the salting-out effect including inorganic salts contained in artificial saliva. It was presumed that it was one of the causes which made it difficult to feel the flavour of the elderly people.

Table 2: Elderly artificial saliva composition and flow.

(g)	1. Std	2.High concentration (30%), half flow (50%)	3. 2 & half mucin
Water	1000	1000	1000
NaHCO ₃	0.397	0.567	0.567
K ₂ HPO ₄	0.645	0.921	0.921
NaCl	0.067	0.0957	0.0957
KCl	0.774	1.11	1.11
CaCl ₂	0.205	0.293	0.293
Mucin	2.16	3.09	1.54
flow rate	1ml/min	0.5ml/min	0.5ml/min

Figure 2: Changes in aroma release due to differences in the strength of mastication, saliva composition and flow.

Conclusion

Studying the effect of coexisting components on the time course behaviour of aroma releases using PTR-MS, it was presumed that there were three major patterns of "top type", "middle type", and "last type" and that they were related to the physicochemical properties of the aroma compounds. In addition, the degree of mastication and lipid content changed, especially the release curves of middle and last type compounds were delayed and suppressed, and it was speculated that mastication degree and matrices including lipids strongly affected flavour release.

As a result of the examination using the elderly person model saliva, the suppression of the aroma release was confirmed by the decrease of the saliva flow rate. The decrease of the salting-out effect was presumed to be a factor, and the decrease of the flavour sensation in the elderly was presumed to be a consequence of the change of the saliva composition.

References

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